

The Project

SUSHEAT is a multi-actor project focused on cutting factory CO₂ emissions and boosting energy efficiency by recycling industrial waste heat and integrating renewable energy sources. With partners spanning 11 European Union countries, the project's goal is to develop and validate a heat upgrade system capable of delivering reliable and flexible industrial heat within a temperature range of 150°C - 250°C.

SUSHEAT will enhance ENERIN's industrial High-Temperature Heat Pump (HT-HP) technology to capture waste heat and convert it into temperatures suitable for intensive manufacturing processes. Novel Thermal Energy Storage (TES) will be integrated into the innovative HT-HP system, alongside a Fresnel Solar Thermal Collector to harness and store solar energy. This innovative approach will be optimised using AI-driven energy management.

The Challenge

Energy-intensive industries in Europe are grappling with high energy costs and the need for carbon-neutral production. Manufacturing, which accounts for 20% of Europe's greenhouse gas emissions, must decarbonise by rethinking energy supply chains, optimising resource use, and managing waste energy - especially in processes that require high-temperature heat currently reliant on fossil fuels.

Partners:

**Sustainable heat upgrade
for net-zero**

Contacts

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**A new generation of highly efficient
AI-powered heat upgrade systems to
harness and store renewable energy,
catering to the high energy demands
of factory processing**

The Solution

SUSHEAT proposes innovative solutions: an industrial heat pump with high-temperature lift, a bio-inspired TES using phase change materials, and an AI-driven decision-making algorithm. These technologies aim to harness renewable and waste energy to deliver heat within the 150°C - 250°C range, adjusting production based on plant demand.

The Objectives

- * Enhance industrial energy efficiency
- * Lower CO₂ emissions and energy use with innovative waste heat upgrades
- * Increase industrial sector flexibility amidst heat electrification
- * Promote industrial heat recovery benefits to key stakeholders

Expected Impacts

With the **SUSHEAT** concept, the expected impact is to reduce annual CO₂ emissions in industrial processes by up to 15 million tonnes, with an expected energy saving of more than 100 Terawatt per hour (TWh) in the European market. Moreover, the **SUSHEAT** project aims to increase energy efficiency in industrial plants and manufacturing processes, as well as enhance grid efficiency.

15 million tonnes

> 100 TWh

1

High-Temperature Heat Pump

The Stirling-based HT-HP captures low-temperature energy sources, converting them into high-temperature heat up to 250°C required for factory processing.

2

Thermal Energy Storage system

Revolutionising TES by selecting optimal materials, developing AI-driven designs, and evaluating them in labs involves choosing the best Phase Change Materials (PCMs), conducting thorough thermophysical characterisation, and applying bio-inspired design principles to achieve a market-ready, efficient system.

3

Control and Integration Twin

The CIT system will incorporate a digital twin for experimental simulations and an AI-guided control system. This integration aims to optimise and enhance energy management for industrial processes through smart decision-making algorithms.

Project facts

Start: May 2023

Duration: 4 years

Budget: €4.67 Million

Consortium: 14 partners